

Homology Modelling of Flap endonuclease 1 protein of *Leishmania donovani* and its Molecular Docking with Novel Inhibitors.

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Leishmaniasis is a parasitic disease caused by an obligate intracellular protozoan from the genus *Leishmania*. *Leishmania donovani*, *L.infantum* and *L.chagasi* are commonly the species that are implicated in the disease. Leishmaniasis is a tropical and a subtropical disease caused by an intracellular parasite transmitted to humans by the bite of a sand fly (*Phlebotomus* and *Lutzomyia*) usually found in Europe, Northern Africa, the Middle East, Asia, and parts of South America. Human Visceral Leishmaniasis is a lethal form of leishmaniasis caused by *Leishmania donovani*, and contributes significantly to the annual burden of infectious diseases of India. The failure of management studies the deadline for the kala azar eradication program from 2012 to 2015 and further upto 2020 and still there is no particular deadline yet due to the ongoing pandemic. *Leishmania* infects three layers of the body namely cutaneous, mucocutaneous and visceral layers involving skin, mucous membranes and visceral organs respectively. The protozoan *Leishmania donovani* requires a particular enzyme Flap Endonuclease I for the DNA replication and repair. It is a structure specific nuclease with 5'-flap endonuclease and 5'-3' exonuclease activities involved in DNA replication and repair. It targets the 5 - overhanging flap endonuclease and cleaves the structure that is generated by the displacement synthesis by DNA polymerase when it encounters the 5'-end of an Okazaki fragment, and also involved in nick ligation. Blocking the action of this enzyme by suitable inhibitor compounds can emerge as a therapeutic approach for the treatment and eradication of the kala azar, and would lead to decreased stability and defective replication of the genome.

Computational methods and Virtual screening for the potential novel inhibitor molecules against the target Flap Endonuclease 1 are very useful for finding a novel drug molecule. In the present study, we have constructed and refined the Flap Endonuclease I structure by homology models based on two different templates; (PDB: 1UL1 and 5ZOD) and then docking the modelled enzyme molecule with the screened potential inhibitor compounds through in-silico studies. A detailed study of the binding energies and properties of the compounds have been done by using Accelrys Discovery Studio 2.1 and Swiss PDB Software.

Keywords: kala azar, Leishmania donovani, Flap Endonuclease I, Accelrys Discovery Studio 2.1, Swiss PDB viewer, virtual screening